

Extraction, Characterization and Phytochemical Screening of the Seed, Seed Oil and Leaves of *Moringa oleifera*

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Abstract:- The seed and leaves of *moringa oleifera*, belonging to the *moringaceae* family which have both nutritional and medicinal applications were studied. Phytochemical screening of five extracts of the plant leaves revealed the presence of alkaloids, saponins, glycosides, flavonoids phenols, and steroids. Quantitative determination of the phytochemicals were carried out and results obtained showed that the percentage content of the alkaloids, saponins, phenols and flavonoids were 0.56%, 0.48%, 0.85% and 4.04% respectively. Chemical characterization of the oils showed that the seed oil had 40.20% yield, 1.122mgKOH/g acid value, 22.842g/100g iodine value, 20.57mg/g saponification value, 270.29 saponification equivalent and no peroxide value. The saponification value indicated that the oil was good for soap, lubricating and pharmaceutical industries. Iodine value indicated that the oil is a non-drying type. No peroxide value indicated the absence of oxidation rancidity. The low acid value indicates that the oil is fresh. The result of the analysis of the thin layer chromatographic fractions of ethylacetate leaf extracts shows absorption at ultraviolet region as well as visible region due to presence of conjugated unsaturation and conjugation with non-bonding electrons. The FTIR spectra analysis of leaf extracts indicated the presence of the major functional groups such as O-H, C-O, C=O, N-H and C=C bonds.

Keywords:- Extraction, Characterization, Phytochemicals, Seed Oil, Leaves of *Moringa Oleifera*.

I. INTRODUCTION

Hundreds of plant species are recognized as having medicinal properties which may be present in one or all the plant parts such as root, stem, bark, leaf, flower, fruit or seeds [Ajiwe et al, 2008; Papiona and Roger, 1978; Strivastava and Viet, 1996]. Plants contain organic metabolites which have been reported to be responsible for remarkable physiological properties [Wog, 1999]. The most important of these bioactive constituents of plants are alkaloids, tannins, flavonoids, steroids, phenols, steroids and glycosides [Akpuaka, 2006 and Finar, 2003]. For example, plants containing alkaloid such as quinine is used for malaria treatment; saponins are used as expectorant; tannins as astringent in diarrhea. Thus, medicinal

plants should be seen as important and basic to the survival of people [Okafor et al,2005].

In developing countries, the use of crude extract of plants is popular. The extensive use of crude plant extracts has not been affected by the presence of orthodox medicine. Based on the World Health Organization estimates, about 80% of the world still relies mainly on traditional medicine for their primary health care needs [Treas and Evans,1989].

Among the many plants and herbs used in Nigeria for the treatment of illness is *moringa oleifera*.

➤ Description of the Plant

The general description of the medicinal plant is given below [Manuel, 1995, Iwu,1993]:

Family: *Moringaceae*

Genus: *Moringa*

Species: *oleifera*

Botanical name: *Moringa oleifera*

Vernacular English name: Horse radish tree, Drumstick tree

Igbo name: Okwe-bekee (okwe-oyibo)

Hausa name: Zogalla-gandi, Danga

Yoruba: Ewe igbale, Idagbo monoye

Moringa oleifera is a small deciduous tree of about 8m high, with pale gray bark and soft woody, originated from India, cultivated throughout all tropical regions from seeds or from cuttings. It flowers and fruits annually and in some regions twice annually. It has a crooked stem that often forks near the base. The twigs and young shoots are densely hairy. The leaves are tripinnate, usually with six pairs of pinnae, large and alternately arranged on the stem. The flowers are small, sweet-scented and borne on loose auxiliary common stalks up to 15cm long; cream coloured with unequal petals that are usually larger than the sepals; the fruits are 3-angled, pod-like, up to 45cm long and 1.3cm broad containing rows of blackish, rounded, oily seeds, each of which has three papery wings [Manuel, 1995, Iwu,1993].

From the available literature, it was found that many research works have been carried out on *moringa oleifera*. The research works involve its chemical composition as well as nutritional, medicinal, industrial and other uses.

Nutritionally, moringa seed oil is used for cooking; leaves and oil press cake are used as cattle fodder; green pods are used as fresh or canned vegetables. Leaves and flowers are used as a relish. The seeds are also eaten green, roasted, powdered and steeped for tea or used in curries [http://www.wikipedia/trees for lifejournal//Moringa oleifera, 2006]. Leaves can be dried, crushed into powder and stored for use as a nutritional additive to soups, salads, rice, sauces etc. before serving [Ghasi et al, 2000].

Medicinally, moringa leaves and pods aid digestion and stimulate appetite. The tender leaves are used for the treatment of scurry, catarrh and given to children suffering from flatulence [Funglie, 1999]. The leaf juice is used to treat anxiety, control glucose level, diarrhea, dysentery, colitis and to increase urine flow. The aqueous leaf extract has anti-ulcerogenic effect [Dahuri et al, 2006]. The leaves and young buds are rubbed on the temple for cure of headache; used as intestinal worm expellant and as a skin antiseptic among many other uses [African Pharmacopeia]. The seed oil is used to treat scurvy, skin diseases, rheumatism, relieve pains and used as a tonic and a purgative [Iwu, 1993].

Industrially, the crusted or powdered seeds are used as a natural coagulant for water purification with 90-99% of bacteria removed [Ghasi, 2000 and Mwangi et al, 2008]. The seed oil is used for machine lubrication and in the manufacture of perfumes and hair care products. Crushed leaves are used as a domestic cleaning agents; the trees are grown as live fences and wind breaks. Its wood can be used as a fuel source [http://www.wikipedia/trees for lifejournal//Moringa oleifera, 2006].

Moringa leaves, flower and fruits have been found to be rich in amino acids, moisture, iron, copper, fat, carbohydrate, fibre; minerals such as calcium, magnesium, potassium and

sulphur; vitamins such as vitamins A, B₁, B₂, B₃, C and E [Iwu, 1993; African Pharmacopeia, 1985]. Moringa oleifera seeds yield 38-40% non-drying oil which is clear, sweet and colourless, never becoming rancid [http://www.theaps.org/medicinalplants.2007, Anwar et al, 2005].

II. EXPERIMENTAL

➤ Sample Collection and Preparation

The fresh leaves of moringa oleifera were collected from the premises of the Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State while the seeds were collected from Dr. Ozumba of the Department of Parasitology and Entomology, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka Anambra State.

The fresh leaves of Moringa oleifera were pounded in mortar to fine paste for phytochemical studies. The seed coats were removed from the dry seeds and the seeds ground using mortar and pestle into a coarse powder.

The phytochemical parameters of the leaf extracts were analysed by Harbone 1998 method [Harbone, 1998]. The oil was extracted from the seeds using soxhlet extractor and then characterized [Official Method of American Oil Chemists Society, 1960]. The ethyl acetate extract of the leaves were analyzed by thin layer chromatography [Ivor and Feinberg, 1965], UV and Fourier Transform Infrared Spectrometry methods [Willard and Merit Dean, 1974].

III. RESULT

The results of the analyses of the active constituents present in the leaves of moringa oleifera and its seed oil characterization are given in tables 1-9.

Table 1: Phytochemical Analysis of the extracts of leaves of Moringa oleifera

Plant Extract	Alkaloids	Saponins	Tannins	Elavonoids	Steroids	Phenols	Glycosides
n-hexane	++	--	-	++	+	-	+
Ethylacetate	+	--	-	+	+	-	+
Water	+	++	-	-	-	+	++
Ethanol	-	++	-	-	+	+	-
Methanol	-	++	-	-	+	-	-

+ = Present in low concentration
 ++ = Present in high concentration
 - = Absent

Table 2: Summary of Quantitative Analysis Result for Phytochemical Constituents of Moringa oleifera leaves

Parameter	Value (%)
Alkaloids	0.56
Saponins	0.48
Phenols	0.85
Flavonoids	4.04

Table 3: Result of the Characterization of the oil Extract from the Seed of Moringa oleifera

Parameter	Value (%)
Yield	40.20%
Acid value	1.222mgKOH/g
Iodine value	22.842g/100g
Saponification value	207.57mg/g
Saponification equivalent	270.29
Peroxide value	Nil

Table 4: The Result of the Retardation Factor of the Thin Layer Chromatography of Ethyl Acetate Extract of the Leaves

Distance moved by Sample (cm)	Solvent front (cm)	Rf Values
0.9	16.2	0.06
3.6	16.2	0.22
6.8	16.2	0.42
11.4	16.2	0.70
15.9	16.2	0.98

Table 5: FTIR and UV spectra for Ethyl acetate extract of Moringa oleifera leaves, fraction I

Absorption band (cm ⁻¹)	Functional Group
3471.02	H-bonded –O-H stretch of alcohols and phenols, N-H stretch for amines and amides
2924.18	C-H stretch of alkyl groups
1448.59	C-H deformation of alkyl groups
1116.82	C-O stretch for alcohols, phenols and ethers
346.23	C-H deformation for alkyl groups
UVλmax	232nm, 253nm, 412nm and 658nm indicating the presence of conjugation

Table 6: FTIR and UV spectra for ethyl acetate extract of moringa oleifera leaves, fraction II

Absorption band (cm ⁻¹)	Functional Group
4310.08	Unbonded O-H
3766.14	O-H stretch of alcohols and phenols
3459.45	H-bonded O-H stretch of alcohols and phenols; N-H stretch for amines and amides
2955.04	C-H stretch for alkyl groups
2924.18	C-H stretch for alkyl groups
2853.78	C-H stretch for alkyl groups
1617.37	C=C stretch of alkenes and aromatics; N-H deformation of amines and amides. C=O stretch for primary amide –CONH ₂ in solution
1377.22	C-H deformation for methyl group, O-H bend of alcohols.
1116.82	C-O stretch for alcohols, phenols and ethers
820.74	C-H absorption of the alkene group R ₂ C=CHR; C-H deformation for 1,3-disubstituted benzene
722.37	C-H absorption of alkenes for the group CHR=CHR; C-H deformation for 1,3-disubstituted benzene
606.63	C-H deformation for alkyl groups
350.09	C-H deformation for alkyl groups
342.38	C-H deformation for alkyl groups
UVλmax	232nm, 274nm, 424nm indicating presence of conjugation

Table 7: FTIR and UV spectra for Ethyl acetate Extract of Moringa oleifera leaves, fraction III

Absorption band (cm ⁻¹)	Functional Group
3380.36	H-bonded -O-H stretch for alcohols and phenols
2871.14	C-H stretch of alkyl groups
2049.43	C≡N stretch for nitriles, RC≡N
1656.91	C=C stretch for alkenes and aromatics; N-H deformation of amines and amides; C=O stretch for secondary amide -CO-NH- in solid state
1447.62	C-H deformation for alkyl groups
1107.18	C-O stretch of ethers, ROH
1027.13	C-H deformation for alcohols
805.31	C-H absorption of alkene group R ₂ C=CHR; C-H deformation of 1,3-disubstituted benzene
616.28	C.H deformation for alkyl groups
475.47	C-H deformation for alky groups
348.16	C-H deformation for alky groups
UVλmax	232nm, 274nm, 364nm and 433nm indicating presence of conjugation

Table 8: FTIR and UV spectra for ethyl acetate Extract of moringa oleifera leaves, fraction IV

Absorption band (cm ⁻¹)	Functional Group
3444.02	H-bonded O-H of alcohols and phenols
2924.18	C-H stretch for alkyl groups -CH ₃ , -CH ₂ , -CH
1619.29	C=C stretch for alkenes and aromatics; N-H deformation of amines RNH ₂ and amides RCONH ₂ ; C=O stretch of primary amides-CONH ₂ in solution
1465.95	C-H deformation for alkyl groups -CH ₃ , -CH ₂ , -CH
1092.71	C-O stretch for alcohols, phenol and ethers
810.13	C-H absorption of alkene group R ₂ C=CHR; C-H deformation of 1,4-disubstituted benzene
449.43	C-H deformation of alkyl groups
356.88	C-H deformation of alkyl groups
UVλmax	232nm, 253nm, 412nm, 658nm indicating the presence of conjugation

Table 9: FTIR and UV spectra for Ethyl acetate Extract of Moringa oleifera leaves, fraction V

Absorption band (cm ⁻¹)	Functional Group
3849.08	Free O-H stretch for alcohols and phenols
3482.59	H-bonded O-H stretch for alcohols and phenols
2924.18	C-H stretch of alkyl groups
1464.98	C-H deformation for alkyl groups -CH ₃ , -CH ₂ , -CH
1377.22	C-H deformation of methyl groups; O-H bend of alcohols
1091.75	C-O stretch for alcohols, phenols, esters, ethers, acids, anhydrides
800.49	C-H absorption for R ₂ C=CHR, C-H out of plane deformations of 1,3-disubstituted benzene ring
714.65	C-H absorption for R ₂ C=CHR, C-H out of plane deformations of 1,3-disubstituted benzene ring
473.54	C-H deformation of alkyl groups
UVλmax	732nm, 784nm, 799nm and 976nm indicating high degree of conjugation

IV. DISCUSSION

The result of the phytochemical screening of the leaves of *Moringa oleifera* showed the presence of alkaloids, saponins, flavonoids, steroids, phenols and glycosides. Tannin is absent which could be due to the nursery plant used. The presence of flavonoids makes *Moringa* leaves suitable for use as a diuretic agent. Flavonoids have antioxidant effect, which could cure cataracts, and antiinflammatory effect; it reduces the risk of heart

and cancer diseases. Alkaloids can be used as painkiller and in the treatment of malaria, cough and cold. Tannins accelerate blood clotting, reduce blood pressure, decrease the serum lipid level, produce liver necrosis and modulate immune responses. Saponins lowers the cholesterol level, reduce the risk of heart disease, improve immune and anticancer functions. Steroids are used in drugs for reducing the risk of coronary heart disease, high blood pressure and cancer. Terpenoids have antioxidant, antiseptic, antibacterial, antifungal and antiinflammatory

properties. Phenols have antioxidant properties against cancer and heart diseases; it also neutralizes free radicals and prevent them from causing cellular damage.

The percentage yield of oil from *Moringa oleifera* seeds is 40.20%. This yield was quite high when compared with many seed oils such as cotton (25-30%), soya bean (15-20%), nutmeg (40%), rubber seed (50%) and shear butter oil (50%) etc suggesting that *Moringa* oil could be used industrially. The extracted oil was liquid at room temperature and solidify at 4-6°C and melted at 6-10.4°C. The colour is clear yellow and fall at 2.25 titanium Disc. The refractive index was 1.465 at 26°C.

Acid value of 1.122mgKOH/g of the oil sample shows that the oil is still fresh and edible and has not stayed for a long time; in other words, low acid and free fatty acid value showed the absence of oxidative rancidity. The iodine value of 22.842g/100g is low specifying that that the oil is saturated or has low degree of unsaturation and as such unsusceptible to oxidative rancidity. The oil is a non-drying oil because its iodine value is below 110. The saponification value of 207.57 is high but compared well with the non-drying oil, indicating that the oil is good for use in soap, lubricating and pharmaceutical industries. There was no peroxide value showing the absence of rancidity i.e there was no autoxidation of the unsaturated fatty acids present in the oil.

The thin layer chromatography of the ethyl acetate leaf extract using diethyl ether: petroleum ether (6:3) as the eluting solvent gave five bands. The retardation factor (R_f value) for each spot of ethyl acetate extract was calculated using the formula.

$$R_f = \frac{\text{dis tan ce moved by sample}}{\text{dis tan ce moved by solvent}}$$

Infrared spectra usually show vibration of the functional groups at the frequency 400-4000cm⁻¹. The absorption bands of hydrogen bonded -O-H of alcohols and phenols as well as N-H stretch for amines and amides were observed between 3200-3600cm⁻¹. Unbounded O-H stretch for alcohols and phenols appeared above 3600cm⁻¹. Absorption bands between 2850-3000cm⁻¹ were due to C-H stretch of alkyl groups. Absorption bands between 1615-1670cm⁻¹ were due to C=C stretch for alkenes and aromatics as well as N-H deformation of amines and amides. C-H deformation of alkyl group occurred between 1415-1465cm⁻¹. The absorption bands between 1380-1370cm⁻¹ were due to the C-H deformation of methyl group and O-H bend of alcohols. The absorption bands between 1050-1300cm⁻¹ were due to C-O stretch for alcohols, phenols, ethers, ester, acids and anhydrides. The absorption bands between 675-730cm⁻¹ were due to C-H absorption of alkenes for the group CHR=CHR and C-H deformation for 1,3-disubstituted benzene. The absorption bands 790-840cm⁻¹ were due to the C-H absorption of the alkene group R₂C=CHR and C-H deformation of 1,3-disubstituted benzene. C-H deformation of alkyl groups appeared between 300-620cm⁻¹.

Ultraviolet-visible radiation absorption is usually from 190nm-800nm, due to π electron system, presence of conjugated unsaturation and conjugation with non-bonding electrons. 190nm-400nm is the ultraviolet region while 400nm-800nm is the visible region. The result of the analysis of the thin layer chromatographic fractions of the ethyl acetate extracts shows absorption at both the ultraviolet region and visible region meaning that there is the presence of high conjugation.

V. CONCLUSION

Moringa oleifera seed oil is an essential oil of the non-drying type with low degree of unsaturation. The phytochemical screening and quantitative analysis of the phytochemicals present in the leaf extracts showed the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, phenols, saponins, steroids, glycosides etc. The quantity of flavonoids was high when compared with the other phytochemicals, hence the use of *Moringa oleifera* as a diuretic (increase urine flow) and an antitumor.

Moringa oleifera is very important for its medicinal, nutritional and industrial value. The medicinal effects of *Moringa oleifera* leaf observed could be due to the action of one or more of the phytochemicals present in the leaf extract which can be attributed to the leaves being anthelmintic, antiulcerogenic and cures hallucinations, dry tumours, hicccough and asthma.

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